

VIEWS ON IMPROVING THE LEGAL CULTURE OF THE ENTREPRENEUR IN CIVIL SOCIETY

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Annotation The article talks about the need to increase the legal culture of entrepreneurs in the conditions of today's civil society, the essence of concepts of entrepreneurship, entrepreneurial activity, entrepreneurial personality, processes of improving their legal regulation mechanisms within the framework of scientific, theoretical and practical research of the problem.

Key words: civil society, entrepreneurs, legal culture, indicators of economic development, small and medium entrepreneurship, entrepreneurship, entrepreneurial activity, entrepreneurial person, rights and freedoms, honor and dignity.

At the global level, special attention is being paid to the establishment of civil society, ensuring the rule of law, as well as increasing the legal culture of entrepreneurs. Today, one of the main indicators of economic development of the countries of the world is undoubtedly explained by the attention to small and medium entrepreneurship. In this regard, the establishment of the Small Business Administration (SBA, Small Business Administration) [1] in the United States in 1953, the global international institution (UNCTAD, WTO, ICC, "The Research by World DataBank, "The World Justice Project", "The Heritage Foundation", "Doing Business", "Transparency International") and the regular publication of rating indicators show that the problem of improving the legal culture of an entrepreneur is of universal importance.

As part of the scientific, theoretical and practical research carried out by the world's scientific research institutes and centers, the essence of concepts of entrepreneurship, entrepreneurial activity, entrepreneurial person, the processes of improving their legal regulation mechanisms, as well as the formation of elements of legal culture in the subjects of entrepreneurial activity, both vertical and horizontal legislation Conclusions of a praxeological nature are emerging on the decision of a strong law enforcement system taking into account liberal values in the system. In this regard, it is necessary to emphasize that in the processes of transformation and modernization of our society, raising the legal culture of the participants of business activities, especially the entrepreneur, and through this, the youth, who make up the main part of our population, is one of the main conditions for the establishment of a legal state.

The socio-philosophical considerations presented above demonstrate the global relevance of the topic. It should be recognized that since 1993, in cooperation with the government of Uzbekistan, among the 177 members of the UN, through the "UNDP Uzbekistan" [2] program, more than a hundred national programs have been implemented for the development of local entrepreneurship.

In the 20th goal of the "New Development Strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026": "Development of an active civil society and formation of a sense of respect and obedience to the law among citizens" [3] was defined as an urgent task. In addition, as the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoev noted: "We must create such a legal culture in our society that compliance with the Constitution and laws, respect for the rights and freedoms, honor and dignity of others is not an obligation, but a daily rule. and should become a habit" [4]. It can be seen that legal culture is an important component of the thinking of citizens, in particular, entrepreneurs. Development of scientific conclusions and practical recommendations that serve to increase the legal culture of an entrepreneur on the basis of normative-legal, traditions, customs and other norms that serve to regulate social, property, cultural, national, economic, corporate and individual relations in the implementation of his activities. appears as an urgent task.

Adoption of the "New Development Strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in order to bring the improvement of public welfare to a new level, as well as "2024 - the year of supporting youth and business" - development of various directions of entrepreneurial activity in our republic We can see it as a logical continuation of systematic reforms to further increase the legal culture of our population, young people, especially entrepreneurs.

The socio-economic and legal essence of the strategic reforms implemented on the development of legal culture lies in the structure of entrepreneurial activity, legal and normative bases that regulate it, professional special culture of an entrepreneur. Judging by historical sources, the roots of entrepreneurial activity go back to the distant past. We know that until the 16th century, the main tributary of the "Great Silk Road" passed through our country, and we can see that trade, trade, and handicrafts developed widely. In this sense, in some national-mental views, the view that entrepreneurship was originally settled in the form of trade has been dominant.

In classical written sources, in particular, in "Avesta", the philosophical and moral thoughts praising human work, condemning laziness, the ideas that teach

hard work, the well-being of society and human life are specially recognized [5]. Also, in the sacred sources of Islam, special attention is paid to entrepreneurship and its religious and legal issues.

Philosophical teachings developed in ancient Greece focused on the issue of entrepreneurship. For example, Plato in his "Laws" - "paying attention to the issue of the relationship between the state and business, it is possible to strengthen the relationship between them only in the conditions of economic freedom" [6], according to the great philosopher Aristotle: "An entrepreneur should engage in fair deeds, regularly engage in good deeds" [7] emphasizes the socialization of entrepreneurship.

The Great Eastern thinker Abu Nasr Farabi in his work entitled "The City of Virtuous People" makes a special mention of open-handed entrepreneurs. According to Farabi, "A community that brings happiness to a person is a truly virtuous, mature, characteristic community. The feeling of caring about the future of a person, his happiness, sharing his sorrows and sufferings should be formed in entrepreneurs" [8]. Abu Nasr Farabi pays special attention to the place of laws in the development of entrepreneurship in society. That's why the Allama said, "The leader should issue laws about trade that will not harm anyone, even about the measurement of weight, the measurement of grains and things like sugar. At the same time, it is necessary for a legislator to reflect the condition of all rich and poor people in the laws, so that the category of people who break the laws and renew evils without correcting their people to the end is not overlooked" [9], he writes. Abu Rayhan Beruni considers the mutual agreement of people to be the main factor in his views on trade (entrepreneurship) [10].

Ibn Sina also explains the importance of legal culture through his thoughts that "...trade (entrepreneurship) should be managed with the help of just laws adopted on the basis of mutual agreement of people" [11]. Amir Temur, a statesman and politician, in his "Temur Rules" states that business relations should be regulated based on the criteria of justice. Also, his words "...I looked at everyone equally seriously and fairly, I did not differentiate anyone from another" [12] are a reflection of the democracy of that time.

The results of the research on the topic show that entrepreneurial activity was mainly formed in the 18th century, and it was often explained in connection with the concept of "proprietor". It is worth noting that the concept of entrepreneurship was given a special definition for the first time by R. Cantilton, a well-known English economist who lived in this period. Later, I. Kant, F. V.

Hegel, J. J. Rousseau, S. L. Montesque showed a special initiative in developing entrepreneurship and its social, legal and philosophical foundations. The following liberal-democratic views of the great French politician, sociologist and philosopher Charles Louis Montesque can be cited: "Freedom does not mean that a person can do what he wants, but it is the right to perform only the actions reflected in the laws, explaining that human activities can be carried out only through laws. " [13] emphasizes. These liberal views serve as an important theoretical-conceptual basis for the development of entrepreneurial activity and the improvement of the legal culture of an entrepreneur even in our time.

Currently, even within the CIS countries, the issue of entrepreneurship is interpreted on the basis of various socio-philosophical concepts. In particular, V.S. Avtonomov explained the entrepreneurial activity based on an anthropological approach and said that "rational decisions of a person and creativity in functional management are useful in entrepreneurship" [14], while G. Simon, the author of the term "limited opportunity" related to entrepreneurial activity, "a certain balance in entrepreneurial activity" and optimal environment is necessary" [15].

M. Alle, laureate of the Nobel Prize in Economics, writes that "the strong rational activity of an entrepreneur reflects personal goals and ways of achieving them" [16]. In this case, an entrepreneur's sincere desire to achieve a certain goal and rational thinking in accordance with it is an important step in achieving effective results.

In short, an entrepreneur with a legal culture takes a close look at the relations that arise in the implementation of his activities, and considers it a simple civic duty to strive to change them in a positive direction. An entrepreneur who does not deeply understand this interdependence and reality cannot realize the noble goals he has set for himself. In order to achieve our final goals, the reforms started in our country should be consistently continued, citizens, especially entrepreneurs, should have a high level of legal awareness, and the legal culture of entrepreneurs should be recognized as a decisive factor in the realization of the principle of "National recovery - national growth".

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